

Social Variables and Attitude to Substance Abuse of Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between social variables (peer influence, family background, and media influence) and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Three research questions and three corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 4,765 senior secondary 3 students in 15 public secondary schools, while a sample of 465 students was selected using a simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument titled Social Variables and Attitude to Substance Abuse Questionnaire (SVSAQ), structured on a four-point rating scale. The instrument was face validated by experts in Guidance and Counselling and Psychological Foundations of Education, and its reliability was established using Cronbach's alpha, and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The instrument was administered with the permission of school authorities, and data collection lasted for one week. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to analyse the data and test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance using SPSS. The findings revealed a very strong positive and significant relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse ($r = 0.849, p < 0.05$), a moderate positive and significant relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse ($r = 0.665, p < 0.05$), and a strong positive and significant relationship between media influence and attitude to substance abuse ($r = 0.717, p < 0.05$). The study concluded that social variables significantly influence students' attitudes toward

substance abuse. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that school counsellors should organise regular peer education and mentoring programmes that promote positive peer influence and discourage substance abuse among students.

Keywords: social variables, attitude, peer influence, family background, social media influence, substance abuse

Introduction

The increasing concern over substance abuse among adolescents in Akwa Ibom State generally and Uyo Local Government Area in particular stems from the researchers' observation of rising cases of drug-related behaviours, smoking, alcohol consumption, misuse of prescription drugs, and other unhealthy practices among secondary school students. These behaviours have continued to disrupt learning environments and expose students to emotional, social, and academic risks. Many adolescents appear to develop favourable dispositions towards substance use through constant interaction with peers, family experiences, and media messages, thus pointing to a deeper concern surrounding their attitude to substance abuse.

Adolescents who develop favourable attitudes towards substance abuse may display truancy, indiscipline, aggression, poor concentration, and withdrawal from academic activities, which affect both their personal development and the school environment. A substance, according to Odejide (2017), refers to any chemical agent that, when introduced into the body, alters normal physiological or psychological functioning, while substance abuse, as defined by Abikoye (2018), is the excessive or improper use of psychoactive substances in a manner that is harmful to the individual's health, social life, or academic functioning. As highlighted by Okafor and Nwoye (2018), substance abuse among adolescents can manifest through behavioural instability, declining academic performance, and increased involvement in risky social activities. They may also experience poor judgement, low self-control, and strained interpersonal relationships. Furthermore, Akinlade and Yusuf (2019) stated that adolescents with favourable attitudes towards substance abuse may become vulnerable to peer pressure, deviant behaviours, and emotional distress. According to Olawole (2022), such students may find it difficult to resist social influence, obey school rules, or make healthy decisions. Over time, these maladaptive attitudes can impair their physical health, social functioning, and future productivity. The emotional and behavioural problems associated with substance abuse may also increase the likelihood of criminal behaviour, mental health challenges, and addiction (Ogunleye & Salawu, 2017). All these points to the critical importance of early identification and intervention to promote healthy attitudes towards substance abuse among adolescents.

According to Adeyemi and Ojo (2019), attitude to substance abuse refers to the beliefs, feelings, and behavioural tendencies individuals hold towards the use of harmful

substances such as alcohol, tobacco, cannabis, and other drugs. Components of attitude to substance abuse include approval or disapproval of drug use, perception of its risks, readiness to resist or accept substance-related offers, and disposition towards drug-taking behaviours. Adolescents with negative attitudes towards substance abuse are more likely to avoid risky behaviours, maintain self-control, and make responsible health choices, which are very necessary for their holistic development.

A healthy attitude towards substance abuse offers a lot of benefits. When adolescents hold negative attitudes toward substance abuse, they may exhibit higher levels of self-discipline, better emotional control, and stronger commitment to academic and social responsibilities. They are less likely to engage in anti-social behaviours such as violence, truancy, cultism, or risky sexual practices. As highlighted by Makanjuola and Adebisi (2020), adolescents with healthy attitudes toward substance abuse tend to demonstrate enhanced self-esteem, sound decision-making, and stronger resilience against negative influences. Such attitudes also prepare adolescents for responsible adulthood by instilling values such as self-control, responsibility, and personal safety, which are critical for functioning effectively in society. However, developing healthy attitudes towards substance abuse is a gradual process which can be influenced by social variables.

Social variables are conditions and social forces within an individual's environment that shape behaviour, perception, and decision-making (Ibrahim, 2018). Social variables could be environmental and interpersonal factors that influence how individuals think, feel, and act in relation to specific issues. In the context of this study, the major social variables considered are peer influence, family background, and social media influence. These factors are important during adolescence because they shape values, choices, and behavioural tendencies.

Peer influence refers to the effect that friends and age mates have on an adolescent's attitudes, beliefs, and behaviour, as stated by Ukaegbu and Edem (2021). Peer influence occurs when adolescents adjust their actions or opinions to align with the expectations or behaviour of their peer group. Adolescents in this category may develop favourable attitudes towards substance abuse when their friends use or approve of drugs. Such individuals may imitate peers in order to gain acceptance, avoid rejection, or feel a sense of belonging. As a result, peer influence can weaken personal judgement and increase the likelihood of experimenting with harmful substances.

On the other hand, family background refers to the nature of the home environment in which adolescents are raised, including parenting style, parental supervision, family values, socio-economic status, and family stability (Salami, 2018). Family background shapes children's attitudes and behaviour because the home serves as the first environment of socialisation. Adolescents from supportive and disciplined homes may develop negative attitudes towards substance abuse, while those from unstable or poorly supervised homes may become more vulnerable to substance use. Such adolescents may struggle with emotional support, guidance, and moral direction, thereby increasing their susceptibility to unhealthy behaviours.

According to Boyd (2019), social media influence refers to the power of online content, interactions, and digital trends to shape how individuals interpret social realities and make personal decisions. Adolescents who are frequently exposed to drug-related content, celebrity behaviour, or peer trends online may gradually develop positive attitudes towards substance abuse. Though social media may provide information and entertainment, it can also normalise harmful behaviours when substance use is portrayed as attractive or socially rewarding. Thus, the type of content adolescents consume online may either discourage or encourage substance abuse.

This study was particularly necessary given the increasing substance-related issues among secondary school students. These unhealthy attitudes and behaviours still manifest despite the efforts made by some parents and secondary school authorities in the Uyo Local Government Area to provide moral instruction, health education, and counselling services to students, which suggests a gap in social and behavioural support. Thus, understanding the link between social variables and adolescents' attitudes to substance abuse can inform the design of intervention programmes such as guidance services, drug education campaigns, and educational policies aimed at addressing substance abuse challenges faced by adolescents in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

The increasing awareness of the dangers of substance abuse notwithstanding, a favourable attitude to substance abuse has remained a visibly pronounced challenge among secondary school students. The researchers' observation revealed frequent incidents of smoking, alcohol use, peer-induced drug experimentation, and other risky behaviours among students. These behaviours not only disrupt the learning environment but also hinder the academic, emotional, and social development of adolescents. Many students appear unable to resist negative peer pressure, evaluate harmful media messages, or cope effectively with challenges within their home environments, suggesting a deeper social problem. While various school programmes attempt to promote discipline and healthy living, they often fail to address the social variables that shape students' attitudes towards substance abuse.

Thus, the need for this study is premised on the alarming rise in cases of substance abuse-related attitudes and behaviours among adolescents in the Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, which have manifested in increasing incidents of school indiscipline, health-risk practices, poor academic performance, and social deviance. Despite various educational reforms, anti-drug campaigns, and counselling interventions put up by some secondary schools, many adolescents continue to develop favourable attitudes towards harmful substances, leading to unhealthy behavioural outcomes. This persistent challenge highlights a critical gap in understanding the social dynamics that shape adolescents' dispositions towards substance abuse, particularly the role of peer influence, family background, and social media influence. Without a deep investigation into how these social variables predict adolescents' attitude to substance abuse, efforts to reduce drug-related problems among students will remain superficial and fruitless.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between social variables and attitude to substance abuse of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the objectives of this study were to determine:

- i. The relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.
- ii. The relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.
- iii. The relationship between social media influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.

Significance of the Study

Through the findings of this study, secondary school students would better understand how social influences affect their attitude towards substance abuse. This knowledge would help them become more self-aware, resistant to negative pressures, and better equipped to make healthy decisions in the face of peer, family, and media-related challenges.

Parents would benefit from the findings of this study by gaining a deeper understanding of how family practices and home conditions influence adolescents' attitudes towards substance abuse. The study would enable them to provide better supervision, respond more effectively to their children's social needs, and create a home environment that discourages harmful behaviours.

More so, teachers would find the outcome of this study helpful in identifying students who may be struggling with drug-related attitudes or exposure to negative social influences. The findings would direct them on how to tailor their classroom management and moral instruction to meet students' developmental needs, promote healthy behaviour, and enhance students' overall academic and social experience.

In addition, guidance counsellors would benefit from the findings of the study, as they play a direct role in supporting students through educational, personal and social challenges. The study would provide them with practical strategies for helping adolescents resist negative peer pressure, cope with harmful media influence, and develop healthier attitudes towards substance abuse.

Finally, future researchers would benefit from the study by accessing data that enriches the academic discussion on social variables and adolescents' attitudes to substance abuse. In other words, the study would serve as a basis for further research while contributing to the existing body of knowledge on adolescent behaviour and substance abuse prevention.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the conduct of the study:

- i. What is the relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students?
- ii. What is the relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students?
- iii. What is the relationship between social media influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

- i. There is no significant relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between social media influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on the relationship between social variables and attitude to substance abuse of secondary school students. Sub-variables of social variables, namely peer influence, family background and social media influence, were the independent variables of this study, while attitude to substance abuse served as the dependent variable. Only senior secondary 3 students in public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State participated in the study.

Theoretical Framework**Social Learning Theory by Albert Bandura (1977)**

Albert Bandura proposed the Social Learning Theory in 1977 as a model that emphasises the importance of observational learning, imitation, and modelling in the development of behaviour and attitudes. According to Bandura, human learning occurs in a social context and can take place purely through observation, even without direct reinforcement. The theory introduced the concept of reciprocal determinism, which states that a person's behaviour, environment, and personal factors interact and influence one another. Bandura also introduced the notion of self-efficacy, defined as one's belief in their ability to resist or carry out a behaviour in a given situation.

This theory is relevant to the present study because it explains how adolescents in the Uyo Local Government Area may develop attitudes towards substance abuse by observing peers, family members, celebrities, and media personalities. For example,

adolescents may imitate drug-related behaviour when they repeatedly observe influential persons engaging in or endorsing such behaviour. Positive models in school, home, or the media may discourage substance abuse, while exposure to deviant peers or harmful online content may encourage favourable attitudes towards it. Therefore, Bandura's theory underscores the role of environmental models and social interaction in shaping adolescents' attitudes to substance abuse.

Theory of Planned Behaviour by Ajzen (1991)

Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (1991) explains that an individual's behaviour is influenced by behavioural intention, which in turn is shaped by attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioural control. 'Attitude' refers to a person's favourable or unfavourable evaluation of a behaviour; 'subjective norm' refers to social pressure from significant others; and 'perceived behavioural control' refers to an individual's belief in their ability to perform or resist a behaviour.

This theory is relevant to the present study because it explains how peer influence, family background, and social media influence may shape adolescents' attitudes to substance abuse. Adolescents may develop favourable attitudes towards substance use when peers approve of it, when family conditions fail to discourage it, or when social media normalises it. Likewise, adolescents who perceive strong social support against substance abuse may develop negative attitudes and stronger resistance. The theory therefore provides a useful explanation for how social variables may predict adolescents' attitude to substance abuse.

Empirical Framework

A study by Adeyemo and Afolabi (2017) explored the relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Ibadan, Nigeria. A total of 320 students were selected through stratified random sampling across six public secondary schools. The researchers used the Peer Influence Scale and the Substance Abuse Attitude Questionnaire for data collection. The study aimed to determine whether association with drug-using peers influenced adolescents' attitude towards substance use. Data analysis using Pearson product moment correlation revealed a significant positive relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse ($r = 0.64$, $p < 0.05$). The authors concluded that adolescents who associate with peers that approve substance use are more likely to develop favourable attitudes towards it. They recommended peer counselling and anti-drug clubs in schools.

In their own study, Nwachukwu and Eze (2018) investigated the influence of family background on attitude to substance abuse among adolescents in Enugu State. The sample comprised 300 secondary school students selected through simple random sampling from five schools. The instruments used were the Family Environment Inventory and the Adolescent Substance Abuse Attitude Scale. Findings from multiple regression analysis indicated that poor parental supervision, unstable homes, and weak family communication

significantly predicted a favourable attitude to substance abuse ($\beta = 0.58, p < 0.05$). The authors concluded that family background plays a significant role in shaping adolescents' perception of drug use and recommended parental education programmes.

Another study by Ojo and Adebisi (2019) explored the effect of social media influence on attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Lagos State. A sample of 350 students was drawn using the cluster sampling technique. The researchers applied the Social Media Exposure Questionnaire and the Drug Abuse Attitude Inventory. The study found a significant positive relationship between exposure to substance-related social media content and favourable attitudes to substance abuse ($r = 0.61, p < 0.05$). The authors emphasised that repeated exposure to online drug-related trends and celebrity influence contributes to the normalisation of substance abuse among adolescents.

A related study conducted by Mensah and Owusu (2020) examined peer pressure and adolescents' attitudes to drug use. A total of 280 students were selected through systematic sampling from urban secondary schools. Data collected using the Peer Conformity Scale and Substance Use Disposition Inventory were analysed with Pearson correlation statistics. The results showed that peer pressure is significantly related to a favourable attitude to drug use ($r = 0.67, p < 0.01$). The study concluded that adolescents often adopt substance-related attitudes in order to gain peer approval and social identity.

In another study, Bello and Kareem (2018) investigated family background and drug use attitude among secondary school students in Ilorin, Nigeria. A sample of 290 respondents was selected using a stratified sampling technique. The Family Background Questionnaire and Attitude towards Substance Use Scale were used for data collection. Data analysis revealed a significant relationship between dysfunctional family background and favourable attitudes to substance abuse ($r = 0.55, p < 0.05$). The study recommended increased parental monitoring and home-based value orientation.

A study by Chukwu and Dominic (2021) examined social media influence and adolescents' disposition to substance abuse in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Using a correlational design, 310 students were selected through simple random sampling. The researchers used the Social Media Influence Inventory and Youth Substance Abuse Attitude Measure. Findings indicated that students who frequently consumed online content that glamorised smoking and alcohol use had more favourable attitudes towards substance abuse ($\beta = 0.62, p < 0.05$). The authors concluded that digital media plays a strong role in shaping adolescents' behavioural attitudes.

From the empirical literature reviewed, it is observed that no study has been conducted on the relationship between social variables and attitude to substance abuse of secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Hence, this present study was conducted to fill the existing gap.

Methodology

Design of the Study

A methodology correlational design was adopted for the study. A correlational research design is useful in determining whether two or more variables are related, as stated by Wali (2004). A correlational research design was considered appropriate for this study because the researcher was interested in establishing the relationship between social variables and attitudes related to substance abuse among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State.

Population of the Study

The Uyo population of the study consisted of 4,765 senior secondary 3 students in 15 public secondary schools in the Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This figure was obtained from the State Uyo Secondary Education Board, Uyo (2026).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A state sample of 465 SS 3 students in public secondary schools in Uyo LGA of Akwa Ibom State was selected for the study using a simple random sampling procedure. The use of the simple random sampling technique will give equal opportunity for any of the students to be selected for the study.

Instrumentation

A researcher-made instrument entitled “Social Variables and Attitude to Substance Abuse Questionnaire” (SVASAQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A consisted of 15 items, and 5 items were used to measure each of the social variable sub-variables, items, namely peer influence, family background and social media influence. Section B consisted of 15 items which measured attitudes to substance abuse of secondary school students in Uyo LGA of Akwa Ibom State. The items contained in the two sections were responded to on a four-point rating scale, namely, sub-variables: Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point.

Validation of Instrument

The, namely, instrument was face-validated by three (3) experts. Two experts in the Department-validated Guidance and Counselling and one from the Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, Faculty of Education, University of Uyo, were selected for the instrument’s validation. The validation of the instrument was done to ensure that the instrument measured what it claimed to measure. In all, the three experts were requested to read through the instrument and vet the items for clarity, relevance and suitability for the study. The inputs from the experts were incorporated into the final draft of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

To instrument and determine the internal consistency reliability of the instrument, the researcher randomly selected 25 SS 3 students who are part of the population but not part of the study sample to respond to the instrument. Data generated were subjected to inter-item analysis using the Cronbach alpha statistic, the Cronbach, and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained.

Method of Data Collection

They administered the instrument to the selected respondents after seeking permission from the principals of each of the selected schools through a letter of introduction from the researcher's institution to carry out the study. Permission obtained from the respective authorities allowed the students to respond to the items in the questionnaire. This exercise lasted for one week.

Method of Data Analysis

Pearson product-moment correlation statistics were used to answer the research questions and also test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 alpha level of significance. Data was subjected to analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

Decision Rule

The following decision rule guided the researcher in answering the research questions:

± 0.10 - ± 0.39 Weak relationship

± 0.40 - ± 0.69 Moderate relationship

± 0.70 - ± 0.79 Strong relationship

± 0.80 - ± 1.00 Very strong relationship

However, if the p-value is less than the statistical 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, but if the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Results

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Peer Influence	465	.849	.000	Very Strong + Relationship; Sig.
Substance Abuse				

The result presented in Table 1 indicates the relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. With a sample size of 465 students, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) of 0.849 shows a very strong positive relationship between peer influence and students' attitude to substance abuse. This implies that as peer influence

increases, the likelihood of a favourable attitude toward substance abuse among students also increases. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient between family background and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Family Background	465	.665	.001	Moderate + Relationship; Sig.
Substance Abuse				

The result in Table 2 reveals that there is a relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. With a sample size of 465 students, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) of 0.665 indicates a moderate positive relationship, suggesting that family background is meaningfully associated with students' attitudes toward substance abuse. The p-value of 0.001, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance, shows that this relationship is statistically significant; therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient between media influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Media Influence	465	.717	.000	Strong + Relationship; Sig.
Substance Abuse				

The result in Table 3 indicates that there is a strong relationship between media influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. With a sample size of 465 students, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) of 0.717 shows a strong positive relationship, implying that increased media influence is associated with a more favourable attitude toward substance abuse among students. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding revealed a very strong positive and significant relationship between peer influence and attitude to substance abuse among secondary school students in the Uyo Local Government Area. This indicates that students who are more influenced by their

peers are more likely to develop favourable attitudes toward substance abuse. A probable reason for this finding is that adolescents are at a developmental stage where they seek acceptance, belonging, and identity within peer groups. As a result, they may conform to group norms and behaviours, including substance use, in order to gain approval and avoid rejection. This finding is consistent with Adeyemo and Afolabi (2017), who found that adolescents who associate with peers that approve substance use tend to develop positive attitudes toward it, as well as Mensah and Owusu (2020), who reported that peer pressure significantly influences adolescents' disposition to drug use.

The second finding showed a moderate positive and significant relationship between family background and attitude to substance abuse. This suggests that students' home environment plays an important role in shaping their attitudes toward substance abuse. A probable reason for this finding is that the family serves as the primary socialisation agent, where values, norms, and behaviours are first learnt. When there is inadequate supervision, poor communication, or instability in the home, students may lack proper guidance and become more susceptible to adopting negative behaviours, including favourable attitudes toward substance abuse. This finding agrees with Nwachukwu and Eze (2018), who found that poor parental supervision and weak family communication significantly predict favourable attitudes to substance abuse, and Bello and Kareem (2018), who also reported a significant relationship between dysfunctional family background and substance abuse attitudes.

The third finding indicated a strong positive and significant relationship between media influence and attitude to substance abuse among students. This implies that increased exposure to media content is associated with more favourable attitudes toward substance abuse. A probable reason for this finding is that media platforms often present substance use in a manner that appears attractive, acceptable, or socially rewarding. Continuous exposure to such content can shape students' perceptions, making substance abuse seem normal or desirable, especially when it is associated with success, popularity, or entertainment. This finding supports the studies of Ojo and Adebisi (2019) and Chukwu and Dominic (2021), who both found that exposure to substance-related media content significantly influences adolescents' attitudes toward drug use.

Conclusion

The study concluded that peer influence, family background, and media influence play crucial roles in either promoting or discouraging favourable attitudes toward substance abuse among students.

Implications for Counselling

The findings of this study have far-reaching implications for counselling practice, particularly within the school system. First, the very strong influence of peers suggests that school counsellors must prioritise interventions that target peer group dynamics. Counsellors should actively identify negative peer clusters and work to restructure them by

promoting positive peer relationships through group counselling, peer mentoring, and leadership programmes. They should also equip students with assertiveness and decision-making skills to resist peer pressure and make independent, healthy choices.

Secondly, the significant role of family background indicates that counselling should not be limited to the student alone but should adopt a more systemic approach. Counsellors need to involve parents and guardians through family counselling sessions, parent-teacher meetings, and awareness programmes. Emphasis should be placed on improving parenting practices, strengthening parent-child communication, and encouraging proper monitoring and supervision at home. This approach ensures that the home environment supports the behavioural changes encouraged in school.

Furthermore, the strong influence of media highlights the need for counsellors to integrate media literacy into their programmes. Students should be guided on how to critically interpret media messages and understand the potential negative effects of substance-related content. Counsellors can organise seminars, workshops, and classroom guidance sessions that help students differentiate between reality and media portrayals, thereby reducing the likelihood of adopting harmful behaviours.

In addition, counsellors should adopt preventive as well as remedial strategies. Preventive counselling should focus on early identification of at-risk students and equipping all students with life skills such as self-control, emotional regulation, and problem-solving. Remedial counselling, on the other hand, should provide support for students who are already exhibiting tendencies toward substance abuse through individual counselling, behavioural modification techniques, and referral services when necessary.

Finally, the findings call for a collaborative approach to counselling. School counsellors should work closely with teachers, school administrators, parents, and community stakeholders to create a supportive environment that discourages substance abuse. This collaborative effort will ensure consistency in guidance across different areas of the students' lives and enhance the overall effectiveness of counselling interventions.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

- i. School counsellors should organise regular peer education and mentoring programmes that promote positive peer influence and discourage substance abuse among students.
- ii. Parents should be educated through workshops and seminars on the importance of providing a supportive home environment, proper supervision, and positive role modelling to reduce students' susceptibility to substance abuse.
- iii. Curriculum planners should incorporate media literacy education into their curriculum to help students develop critical thinking skills that enable them to resist negative media influence related to substance abuse.

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SOCIAL VARIABLES AND ATTITUDE TO SUBSTANCE ABUSE QUESTIONNAIRE (SVASAQ)

INSTRUCTION: Choose your responses as they best appeal to you by ticking appropriately in the boxes provided below.

KEY: The response options are Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD)

Section A: Social Variables

S/N	Peer Influence	SA	A	D	SD
1.	I feel pressured by my friends to try substances to abuse substances.				
2.	I am use substances when my friends are involved.				
3.	My friends encourage behaviours that involve substance use.				
4.	I find it difficult to refuse when my peers offer me substances.				
5.	I admire friends who engage in substance use.				
	Family Background				
6.	My family values influence my attitude towards substance use.				
7.	My home environment encourages substance abuse.				
8.	Lack of parental attention can influence substance use among students.				
9.	Members of my family use substances.				
10.	Family conflicts can lead adolescents to substance abuse.				
	Social Media Influence				
11.	I often see posts about substance use on social media.				
12.	Social media makes substance use appear attractive.				
13.	I have seen celebrities promoting substances online.				
14.	I learn about substances through online platforms.				
15.	I feel curious about substances after seeing them on social media.				

Section B: Attitude to Substance Abuse

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1.	Substance use is harmful to my health.				
2.	I would never consider using illegal substances.				
3.	Substance abuse can destroy a person's future.				
4.	I see nothing wrong with taking alcohol occasionally.				
5.	I believe substance use makes people feel better.				
6.	I feel that using drugs can solve personal problems.				
7.	I feel that using drugs can solve personal problems.				
8.	I feel uncomfortable around people who use substances.				
9.	I think it is acceptable for students to drink alcohol.				
10.	I think students use substances because of curiosity.				
11.	I feel confident in my ability to avoid substance use.				
12.	I believe drug use can damage relationships.				
13.	I think substance abuse is a serious problem among students.				
14.	I think substance use is a way of coping with stress.				
15.	It is not totally wrong for students to use substances.				